

1 **Ultrasonic Investigation of granular materials subjected to**
2 **compression and crushing**

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19 **Abstract:**

20 Ultrasonic wave propagation measurement has been used as a suitable technique for studying the
21 granular materials and investigating the soil fabric structure, the grain contact stiffness, frictional
22 strength, and inter-particle contact area. Previous studies have focused on the variations of shear
23 and compressional wave velocities with effective stress and void ratio, and lesser effort has been
24 made in understanding the variation of amplitude and dominant frequency of transmitted waves
25 with deformation of soil packing. In this study, continuous ultrasonic wave transmission
26 measurements during compaction of unconsolidated quartz sand are used to investigate the impact
27 of soil layer deformation on ultrasonic wave properties. The test setup consisted of a loading
28 machine to apply constant loading rate to a sand layer (granular quartz) of 6 mm thickness
29 compressed between two forcing blocks, and an ultrasonic wave measurement system to
30 continuously monitor the soil layer during compression up to 48 MPa normal stress. The variations
31 in compressional wave attributes such as wave velocity, transmitted amplitude, and dominant
32 frequency were studied as a function of the applied normal stress and the measured normal strain
33 as well as void ratio and particle size. An increasing trend was observed for P-wave velocity,
34 transmitted amplitude and dominant frequency with normal stress. In specimen with the largest
35 particle size ($D_{50}=0.32\text{mm}$), the wave velocity, amplitude and dominant frequency were found to
36 increase about 230%, 4700 % and 320 % as the normal stress reached the value of 48 MPa. The
37 absolute values of transmitted wave amplitude and dominant frequency were greater for specimens
38 with smaller particle sizes while the normalized values indicate an opposite trend. The changes in
39 the transmitted amplitude were linked to the changes in the true contact area between the particles
40 with a transitional point in the slope of normalized amplitude, coinciding with the yield stress of
41 the granular soil layer. The amount of grain crushing as a result of increase in the normal stress

42 was experimentally measured and a linear correlation was found between the degree of grain
43 crushing and the changes in the normalized dominant frequency of compressional waves.

44 **Keywords:** Granular material, Compression, particle crushing, Ultrasonic properties, Amplitude,
45 Dominant frequency.

46 **1- Introduction:**

47 The deformation of granular soil layers has been always introduced as a critical topic in
48 geotechnical engineering from tunneling and underground construction to design of building
49 foundations and earth dam embankments [1-2]. The particle scale mechanisms happening in
50 granular materials including elastic deformation of particles [3] particles arrangement [4] and grain
51 crushing [5-8] lead to complicated deformation patterns in wide range of strains, from 10^{-6} to 10^{-3}
52 in laboratory and field condition. These mechanisms depend on grain to grain contact network and
53 stress level at surface of each individual particle. In granular soil layers, applied stresses are mainly
54 carried by a series of particles forming a continuous path known as force chain, while other
55 particles act as supports for the previously formed force chains [9-12]. Force chains form in an
56 inhomogeneous pattern and are stable in early stages of compression experiencing elastic
57 deformation which results in a slight increase in inter-particle contact area [13,14]. However, as
58 the boundary stresses increase, the force chains first experience buckling and then particle crushing
59 occurs as the contact stresses exceed the strength of a single particle [15,16].

60 Acoustic emission has been identified and widely used as a nondestructive method to assess
61 particle crushing, fracturing and deformation in granular and specially in rock materials [17,18].

62 Acoustic emission provides valuable insights to fracturing mechanisms of rock materials [19],
63 however, for soil materials the amount of released acoustic energy during particle crushing is small
64 and therefore not always fully detectable [20]. An alternative method to acoustic emission is

65 application of an active ultrasonic wave propagation in granular materials, which was found as a
66 successful method for imaging the structure of granular packing and soil particles [21-27].
67 Ultrasonic energy transmits through rock and granular materials with elastic deformation of
68 particles. For granular materials, transmitted waves are dependent on the bulk and shear stiffness
69 of individual particles and elastic properties of soil assembly, while for rock materials the
70 properties of transmitted wave is dependent on the volume, geometry and distribution of pores and
71 fractures [28-30].

72 Ultrasonic wave amplitude in granular media provides insights on how soil structure varies under
73 external loading and deformations. Variations of ultrasonic transmitted amplitude in granular and
74 rock materials have been investigated through shear and compression experimental tests. Shear
75 loading on rock and granular materials leads to multiple increasing-decreasing trends in values of
76 transmitted amplitude, while during compression an increasing trend was observed with increasing
77 confining stress [31]. In addition to the confining stress, the amplitude of transmitted waves
78 depends on inter-particle contact area in granular material which is a function of particles shape,
79 particle size and void ratio [32,33,21]. This dependency of wave amplitude on geometrical particle
80 properties results in significant changes in ability of soil layers to transmit ultrasonic wave energy
81 [31].

82 Changes in the soil particle sizes lead to changes in volume and distribution of pore size in the soil
83 structure and consequently variations in the dominant frequency of transmitted waves. Dominant
84 frequency of ultrasonic waves was measured during compression and shear loading in granular
85 and rock materials [34-37]. Dominant frequency variations in rock specimens are related to the
86 fracture properties and aperture distribution in rock specimens. Fractures and voids in rock and
87 granular materials have two major impacts on the signals: (a) the fracture attenuates the signal and

88 (b) the fracture filters the high frequency content of the transmitted wave [38]. In fractured rocks,
89 seismic wave propagation is sensitive to the number of fractures, distribution and amount of
90 contact area within a fracture, therefore different frequencies are able to image different subset of
91 fracture or voids in rock joint and soil specimens respectively [39-41].

92 Ultrasonic wave velocity measurements have been used to provide insights about micro properties
93 of soil and rock materials. Variations in ultrasonic wave velocity was observed to be related to the
94 bulk, shear and contact stiffness of individual soil particles as well as inter-particle forces and soil
95 particle arrangements [42,43]. Several studies have focused on using the micro seismic properties
96 of soil particles for evaluating the bulk and shear stiffness of soil layers [44,45]. In other attempts,
97 variations in ultrasonic wave velocity were related to pore collapse and grain crushing in sand and
98 sandstone materials [46-48]. These experimental works related the observed rate of variations in
99 shear and compressional wave velocities during compression to (a) particle crushing and (b)
100 porosity reduction [48]. However, other experimental studies have indicated that wave velocity is
101 independent of particle sizes and the increase in wave velocity during compression is related to
102 normal stress increment and porosity reduction [49,50].

103 In granular materials, much efforts have been paid to understand the effect of mechanical
104 deformation of soil particles on shear and compressional wave velocity rather than transmitted
105 amplitude and dominant frequency, while the impact of controlling deformation mechanisms of
106 granular soil assemblies have not been clearly detected in compressional and shear wave velocities
107 and lead to an important question: How deformation mechanisms in granular materials are
108 represented in ultrasonic wave properties?

109 The study presented herein aims to link the transmitted seismic wave amplitude and dominant
110 frequency to the yield stress and particles crushing of soil specimens composed of Ottawa quartz

111 sand with different particle sizes and void ratios. For this purpose, a conventional one dimensional
112 compression and a novel ultrasonic wave propagation system were utilized to mechanically apply
113 desired normal stress levels and also propagate the compressional waves through the granular layer
114 as it is subjected to compression. The one dimensional compression system can apply normal stress
115 up to 48 MPa while the contact stress between the transducers and soil specimen assembly was
116 kept constant throughout the test. In previous studies, it was found that changes in maximum
117 transmitted amplitude and dominant frequency in granular materials are dependent on contact area
118 and size of the pores between the particles. Several tests including multiple compression and
119 unloading cycles on three different particle sizes were conducted to identify the impact of normal
120 stress, particle size, void ratio and stress history on the evolution of contact area and reduction in
121 size of inter-particle pores. Changes in values of transmitted amplitude were used to qualitatively
122 compare the soil specimens compressibility and evolution of contact area during compression. In
123 addition, compression tests with different ultimate normal stresses were conducted to measure the
124 amount of particle crushing with respect to the applied normal stress and investigate the relations
125 between wave attributes and particle crushing for different particle sizes. It is shown that in
126 addition to the wave velocity, transmitted amplitude and dominant frequency can provide valuable
127 insights to physical mechanisms in granular materials and ultrasonic wave propagation
128 measurement is an appropriate approach to assess deformation of granular soil layers.

129

130 **2- Experimental setup**

131 **2-1 One dimensional compression setup**

132 The configuration for one dimensional compression device designed for this study is schematically
133 shown in Figure 1. This configuration consists of a loading machine to apply high levels of normal

134 stress (up to 48 MPa) with a constant loading rate, an assembly of transducer holder plates and
135 forcing blocks to place the transducers and soil specimen, and a novel ultrasonic system to transmit
136 and receive compressional and shear waves.

137 The vertical loading frame is manufactured by Controls Co. with a moving bottom platen which
138 is capable of applying the normal load up to 4000 kN. Normal displacements were recorded using
139 three linear variable differential transformers (LVDT) placed between the bottom and top platen
140 of the loading frame with 120 degrees apart from each other. Load cell and LVDTs recordings
141 were used to measure the changes in the applied normal stress and the void ratio during one
142 dimensional compression tests.

143 As illustrated in Figure 1, the ultrasonic system involves two arrays of transducers placed at the
144 two sides of the soil specimen. These transducers were designed to send and receive waves while
145 they are in contact with a rigid material, as the forcing block. Two stainless steel plates were
146 designed and manufactured to transfer the normal stress to the soil specimen and allow for
147 placement of transducers around the soil layer.

148 To allow for good transmission of waves from source through the soil specimen, a good coupling
149 between the transducer and forcing block is required. A thin layer of oven-baked honey as the
150 coupling material was applied to the transducers. The honey was baked for 90 minutes at 90 °C to
151 reduce the water content [51]. To have an equal and constant contact stress, a spring washer and a
152 series of stainless steel shims with thickness of 0.001 inch were placed underneath each transducer
153 in a way that final surface of all transducers is 2 mm above the final surface of aluminum cover
154 plate (see Figure 1). The washer was compressible and as the normal load reached to 70 lb, it
155 became flat and made the transducer to be at the same height as the aluminum cover plate

156 (see Figure 1). By using this method, the contact stress between the forcing block and all
157 transducers will be constant and independent of loading and unloading cycles.

158
159

160
161 Figure 1- schematic and detailed view of one dimensional compression set-up including
162 transducer holder plates, ultrasonic transducers and soil specimen

163

164 2-2 Ultrasonic measurements

165 An ultrasonic wave measurement system with two arrays each including 5 transducers was used
166 to record transmitted wave forms through the soil specimen. We used 1 inch cylindrical contact
167 transducers (Olympus V103 and V153) with central frequency of 1MHz and a pulser-receiver
168 (Olympus Panametrics 5077PR) to generate signals with amplitude of 300 volts at repetition rate
169 of 5 kHz. Transmitted waveforms for all 5 transducers were recorded with a fast labView
170 controlled data acquisition system and a digitizer manufactured by National instrument Inc. (NI-
171 PXI 5142) with sampling rate of 100 million samples per second.

172 Compressional and shear waves with 2 seconds intervals (imaging frequency of 0.5 Hz) were
173 transmitted through the soil specimen, while the normal stress was kept constant. The perfect

174 reproducibility of the recorded pulses in amplitude and arrival time during a 10 minutes' time
 175 period showed that the excitation amplitude is small enough to prevent particles disturbance caused
 176 by large vibration amplitudes, as verified in similar work such as [23].
 177 In this study, coupling material between the forcing block and transducers, specimen preparation
 178 and testing procedure were repeated systematically for all tests. Additionally, the contact stress
 179 between the transducer and forcing block was equal and similar for all transducers as well as being
 180 independent of applied normal stress on the specimen. Therefore, the variations in values of
 181 transmitted amplitude, velocity and dominant frequency were solely due to changes in properties
 182 of soil specimen as the repeatability of obtained results were controlled for similar samples.
 183 Compressional and shear waves were recorded during the experiment and simultaneous with the
 184 application of stress paths. Figure 2 shows the series of waveforms collected at different values of
 185 applied normal stress for a compression (Figure 2a) and a shear transducer (Figure 2b). Variations
 186 in wave attenuation and dispersion resulting from changes in properties of specimen composed of
 187 quartz sand ($D_{50}=0.32$ mm) with normal stress leads to changes in wave forms, transmitted
 188 amplitude and arrival time as shown in Figure 2.

189
 190 Figure 2- Examples of recorded a) Compressional, and b) Shear wave forms in two different
 191 normal stress levels.

192 Key characteristics of ultrasonic waves including maximum transmitted amplitude, wave velocity,
 193 and dominant frequency were studied. Maximum transmitted amplitude was obtained as the
 194 maximum value in the first peak of the signal, and arrival time was marked as the first point where
 195 the excitation emerges from the background noise, as suggested by [52,53]. Wave velocity was
 196 then determined according to the sample thickness at the corresponding stress level. Dominant
 197 frequency is determined using the Fourier Transform to transfer the time domain wavelet into its
 198 frequency domain components. In particulate materials such as quartz sand, transmitted
 199 waveforms are not clear and should be analyzed locally to capture the true changes in dominant
 200 frequency. Thus, we used the taper function (Figure 3a) to separate initial part of the recorded
 201 signal from the subsequent variations while keeping the frequency content and wave forms
 202 unaffected [40,54]. A taper and a window size of 5.12 microseconds were applied on the original
 203 wave form after several iterations and then Fourier Transform was operated on the appropriate
 204 window size of tapered waveforms. Dominant frequency was determined as the corresponding
 205 frequency to the maximum amplitude in the frequency domain (Figure 3b).

206
 207 Figure 3- Illustration of a) window size, taper and b) dominant frequency determination method.

208 **2-3 Tested materials**

209 Experiments were conducted on granular layers composed of pure quartz sand (SiO_2) obtained
210 from US Silica Company, Ottawa Illinois. The material is yellowish brown with specific gravity
211 of 2.65. Ottawa sand was selected for experiments as it is a common standard granular material
212 and its mechanical properties have been widely investigated by [55-57].
213 The material is commercially branded as F75 and includes wide range of grain sizes. In order to
214 have uniform soil types, the purchased soil was initially sieved based on ASTM C136 [58] standard
215 and three different uniform fine grain samples with different mean grain size was collected and
216 identified as sand No. I (mean grain size of 0.32 mm), No. II (mean grain size of 0.20 mm) and
217 No. III (mean grain size of 0.10 mm). Angularity of sand particles were determined as sub-angular
218 using scanning electron microscope, SEM images, as shown in Figure 4. Particle size distribution
219 curves and typical properties of sand particles are summarized in Figure 5 and table 1. Based on
220 the calculated coefficient of uniformity and coefficient of curvature, all three sand types were
221 described as poorly graded sand, SP, in accordance to Unified Soil Classification System, USCS
222 (ASTM D2488-00) [59].

223
224 Figure 4- SEM images with 100 times magnification for three Ottawa sand specimens before
225 compression; (a) soil type I, $D_{50} = 0.32$ mm, (b) soil type II, $D_{50} = 0.20$ mm, (c) soil type III, $D_{50} =$
226 0.10 mm

227

228

Figure 5- Grain size distribution curves for three Ottawa sand specimens before compression.

229

230

231

Table 1- Geotechnical properties of tested materials

Property	Description		
	Sand No. I	Sand No. II	Sand No. III
Mineral	99% SiO ₂	99% SiO ₂	99% SiO ₂
Grain shape	Sub-angular	Sub-angular	Sub-angular
Specific gravity, G _s	2.65	2.65	2.65
Mean particle size, D ₅₀ (mm)	0.32	0.20	0.10
Coefficient of curvature, C _C	0.97	0.95	0.92
Coefficient of uniformity, C _u	1.17	1.16	1.37

232

233 2-4 Specimen preparation

234 To prepare specimens, soil particles were initially dried in an oven at 95 °C for 24 hours. De-aired

235 water was added and uniformly mixed with the dried soil to give water content of 10% and then

236 the soil was equalized in a sealed plastic for 24 hours. Thereafter, the 6 mm specimen was

237 constructed in two layers on the square 10 cm by 10 cm grooved stainless steel forcing block. A
 238 leveling lab-jack and four plastic bars were used to control the specimen height and construct the
 239 specimen with desired void ratio. A cellophane tape around the forcing blocks was used to prevent
 240 loss of materials during specimen preparation.

241

242 **2-5 Testing program and procedure**

243 The stress path for first series of experiments include two cycles of compression loading and
 244 unloading. In the first cycle, specimens were loaded up to 28 MPa and then unloaded to 3 MPa
 245 normal stress with a constant rate of 0.2 MPa/s. The first cycle was then followed with another
 246 compression-unloading cycle with similar loading rate and maximum normal stress of 48 MPa to
 247 assess the role of pre-compression on the ultrasonic wave properties. Six specimens composed of
 248 sand No. I, II and III prepared in two different void ratios of 0.48 and 0.65 were subjected to this
 249 stress path to explore the impact of particle size and initial void ratio on the specimen mechanical
 250 behavior and subsequently ultrasonic measurements. The experimental program and initial
 251 properties of specimens are outlined in table 2. The designation system consists of two parts. The
 252 first part indicates the specimen properties including density of the specimen, Dense or Loose, as
 253 well as soil type, S1, S2 or S3. The second part describes the stress path and includes number of
 254 loading cycles and maximum normal load in the first loading cycle.

255

256 Table 2- Experimental program for the first series of compressional tests

Name	Initial void ratio	Mean particle size	number of loading/unloading cycles	Maximum normal stress in the first cycle	Maximum normal stress in the second cycle
DS1-2C28	0.48	0.32	2	28	48
DS2-2C28	0.48	0.20	2	28	48

DS3-2C28	0.48	0.10	2	28	48
LS1-2C28	0.65	0.32	2	28	48
LS2-2C28	0.65	0.20	2	28	48
LS3-2C28	0.65	0.10	2	28	48

257

258 Second series of tests was carried out with the objective of identifying the impact of grain crushing
259 on the ultrasonic waves. Grain crushing plays a critical role in yield stress and deformation of sand
260 specimens and potentially on the ultrasonic wave properties. Several researchers have related the
261 constitutive behavior of sand layers to fracture strength and properties of a single particle including
262 mineralogy and size [8,60,61]. In this study, to identify the impact of particle size and confining
263 stress, fifteen specimens composed of sand No I, II and III, were prepared with the same initial
264 void ratio and subjected to 10, 20, 30, 40 and 48 MPa normal stress. Ultrasonic measurements
265 were conducted during all experiments and particle size distribution was determined using sieve
266 analysis on tested specimens.

267 Table 3- Experimental program for the second series of compressional tests

Name	Initial void ratio	Mean particle size	Number of loading/unloading cycles	Maximum normal stress in the first cycle	Maximum normal stress in the second cycle
DS1-1C10	0.48	0.32	1	10	-
DS1-1C20	0.48	0.32	1	20	-
DS1-1C30	0.48	0.32	1	30	-
DS1-1C40	0.48	0.32	1	40	-
DS1-1C48	0.48	0.32	1	48	-
DS2-1C10	0.48	0.20	1	10	-
DS2-1C20	0.48	0.20	1	20	-
DS2-1C30	0.48	0.20	1	30	-
DS2-1C40	0.48	0.20	1	40	-
DS2-1C48	0.48	0.20	1	48	-
DS3-1C10	0.48	0.10	1	10	-
DS3-1C20	0.48	0.10	1	20	-
DS3-1C30	0.48	0.10	1	30	-
DS3-1C40	0.48	0.10	1	40	-
DS3-1C48	0.48	0.10	1	48	-

268

269 3- Results

270 Compression and deformation of granular material under static and dynamic loads is the result of
271 several mechanisms. These include the particle scale mechanisms such as particles movements
272 and grain crushing as well as developing particle contact network and deformation of force chains
273 [13-63]. During compression, contact network and force chains experience multiple compression
274 and reformations as the confining stress increases. These changes occur with particles restructuring
275 and particle comminution resulting in soil layer settlement, a tighter structure, lower void ratio and
276 higher particle coordination number [64]. An increase in particle coordination number, average
277 number of contact points between particles, tends to increase the contact area between the particles,
278 resulting an increase in transmitted amplitude of ultrasonic waves and lowering the ultrasonic wave
279 path resulting an increase in wave velocity [65,66]. According to previous studies, changes in
280 dynamic bulk stiffness with confining stress and normal strain is related to wave velocity, contact
281 stiffness and inter-particle stresses as well as particle coordination number [42]. However,
282 deformation of sandy soils is more because of rearrangement of soil particle, and particles crushing
283 rather than contact stiffness of the particles. The stress-strain curve obtained for test DS1-2C28
284 and the associated changes in the transmitted amplitude, wave velocity and dominant frequency
285 are shown in Figure 6(a–d). This graph shows a general consistency between the variation of
286 transmitted amplitude and normal stress during loading and unloading cycles. This consistency,
287 indicates that the impact of mechanisms affecting the compressional behavior of sandy soils could
288 be represented in maximum transmitted amplitude of ultrasonic waves traveling through the soil
289 specimen, while dominant frequency and P-wave velocity follow a different trend from stress-
290 strain curve.

291 Compression behavior of sand specimens under external stresses is a function of particle size, void
292 ratio and stiffness of single particles as well as chemical properties of individual particle and

293 bonding between the particles [67,68]. In this study, we focused on the physical properties of sand
 294 specimens and kept the chemical properties unchanged. In the following sections, the effect of
 295 physical properties of sand specimens including initial void ratio, particle size and particle
 296 crushing on the yield stress and mechanical behavior of sand specimens were identified and then
 297 the variations were linked to the ultrasonic measurements.

298

299 Figure 6 – Example of variations in ultrasonic wave properties during compression of sand No. I.
 300 Changes in a) normal stress b) peak transmitted amplitude c) P-wave velocity d) dominant frequency,
 301 with normal strain.

302

303 3-1 Effect of initial void ratio

304 The first series of tests was conducted with the objective of identifying the impact of particles
 305 arrangement and initial void ratio on the mechanical behavior of soil specimen and corresponding

306 changes in ultrasonic measurements. In these experiments, a loose and a dense sand specimen with
307 different initial void ratios of 0.65 and 0.48 were prepared, respectively. For each specimen, two
308 cycles of compression-unloading with constant loading rate were performed to consider the impact
309 of pre-compacted structure and stress history on variation of transmitted wave's amplitude,
310 velocity, and dominant frequency. In the first cycle of loading, normal stress was raised up to 28
311 MPa and unloaded to 3 MPa, and then in the second loading cycle the normal stress was raised up
312 to 48 MPa and unloaded to 3 MPa. Compression tests following this stress path were performed
313 on all three sand types with different initial void ratios to validate the obtained results for soils
314 with different particle size distribution. Evolution in transmitted amplitude, wave velocity and
315 changes in void ratio during the compression and unloading cycles for specimen DS1-2C28 and
316 LS1-2C28 are presented in Figure 7 (a-d).

317 The variation of void ratio with normal stress for two specimens composed of sand No. I and No.
318 II with different initial void ratios are shown in Figure 7(a). In low level of stresses (less than 10
319 MPa), the void ratio decreases slightly with increase in normal stress, these reductions in volume
320 and void ratio is more related to elastic deformation of soil particles and force chains [62]. In
321 contrast, beyond the yield stress, rate of changes in void ratio increases and soil specimen
322 deformation is considered as almost plastic or nonreversible compression. Nonreversible
323 deformation is due to the slippage happening between particles and also evolutionary grain
324 crushing with normal stress. Yield stress is the corresponding stress to maximum curvature and is
325 determined by passing two tangential lines to initial and final slope of compression curve [7].

326 Evolution of transmitted amplitude was recorded during compression and are presented in Figure
327 7(b). Absolute values of transmitted amplitude are greater for the specimen with lower initial void
328 ratio. The coordination number, has a reverse relationship with void ratio and increases with

329 decreasing void ratio. Coordination number for a particle is defined as the average number of
 330 contact points with neighbor particles. The following equation is suggested by [69] Fields (1963)
 331 for coordination number:

$$C_n = \frac{12}{1+e} \quad (1)$$

332
 333 According to equation 1, particle coordination number in specimen DS1-2C28 is more and
 334 therefore the number of contact points and subsequently inter-particle contact area for a unit of
 335 surface area is higher. This increase in inter-particle contact area leads to an increase in values of
 336 transmitted amplitude through the soil specimen. Transmitted amplitude follows an increasing
 337 trend with normal stress in both specimens, however the rate of changes is not constant and
 338 increases with normal stress.

340 Figure 7- Impact of initial void ratio on: a) void ratio and values of yield stress, b) absolute
341 values of transmitted amplitude, c) wave velocity, d) dominant frequency during compression
342 and unloading cycles.

343 Compressional wave velocity values are presented in Figure 7(c). The values indicate an increasing
344 trend with normal stress during compression. Wave velocity is a function of properties of solid
345 particles, contact network and force chain arrangements [43, 70, 71]. In this case, because the soil
346 particles in both specimens are similar, the difference in obtained values of wave velocities are
347 related to the difference in void ratio and arrangement of particles. Wave velocity is higher in
348 specimen with lower initial void ratio as the wave travel length reduces with increasing number of
349 in contact particles [50, 66]. During the unloading path, wave velocity decreases nonlinearly with
350 normal stress; however, the values are slightly greater than the corresponding values in the
351 compression, as soil particles have experienced particle rearrangement and grain crushing during
352 the first loading cycle.

353 Dominant frequency of transmitted waves was derived by operating fast Fourier transform on the
354 recorded waveforms. Obtained results for dominant frequency variation of tests DS1-2C28 and
355 LS1-2C28 are shown in Figure 7(d). Dominant frequency for transmitted waves increases in a
356 nonlinear manner with normal stress in both specimens, and in contrast to maximum transmitted
357 amplitude, rate of increase in dominant frequency decreases gradually and the values tend to
358 approach a horizontal asymptote as the normal stress increases. The horizontal asymptote appears
359 to depend on the void ratio and arrangement of soil particles. For the specimen with higher void
360 ratio dominant frequency of transmitted waves has lower values as there are more number of inter-
361 particle pores with larger volumes [50].

362 In the first unloading stress path (Figure 7), from 28 MPa to 3 MPa, dominant frequency and
363 transmitted amplitude decrease with a significantly milder slope compare to the loading path, and
364 the values are not fully recovered at 3 MPa normal stress. On the other hand, wave velocity values
365 in the unloading paths specially at low levels of normal stress are close to the measured values in
366 loading path, which shows that wave velocity is more dependent on normal stress rather than soil
367 structure [72-73].

368 In the second cycle, for normal stresses lower than 28 MPa, wave velocity, maximum transmitted
369 amplitude and dominant frequency follow the same trend as obtained in the previous unloading
370 path. For normal stresses higher than 28 MPa, the rate of increase in maximum transmitted
371 amplitude slightly increases consistent with deformation of soil specimen and changes in void
372 ratio, while rate of increase in wave velocity does not show similar changes (Figure 7).

373 The great repeatability observed for the maximum transmitted amplitude values, wave velocity
374 and dominant frequency in the second cycle for normal stresses lower than 28 MPa provide
375 evidence that soil structure does not change in the second reloading path and effect of stress history
376 is represented in ultrasonic wave properties.

377 In the major unloading path, 48 to 3 MPa (Figure 7), wave velocity and maximum transmitted
378 amplitude are higher as the soil particles were subjected to additional compression for normal
379 stresses of 28 to 48 MPa. Also, the difference between the obtained values in second loading and
380 unloading stress path is more for normal stresses higher than 28 MPa. However, in the major
381 unloading stress path dominant frequency values experience a constant upward shift respect to the
382 loading path.

383 Note that in order to confirm the observations for sand No. I, similar experiments were carried out
384 on sand No II and No. III and the same observations were made for the effect of initial void ratio.

385 Figure 8 shows the variation of normalized transmitted amplitude as a function of normal stress
386 for specimen DS1-2C28 and LS1-2C28. The maximum transmitted amplitude was normalized
387 with respect to the its initial value at the beginning of the test. As shown in this Figure, the
388 normalized values increased nonlinearly as the normal stress was applied on the specimens. Values
389 of normalized transmitted amplitude followed an opposite trend from the absolute amplitude
390 values and were more for specimen LS1-2C28. Normalized transmitted amplitude shows the
391 evolution of true contact area between the particles in which several mechanisms including elastic
392 deformation of particles and force chains, particles slippage and rearrangement, and particle
393 crushing and reformation of force chains are involved as in void ratio variation. Normalized
394 transmitted amplitude also provide valuable insights to compressibility of soil specimen as
395 evolution in inter-particle contact area is the result of soil layer compression and specimen with
396 higher void ratio experience higher amount of increase in normalized amplitude. Specimen DS1-
397 2C28 experienced 0.33 reduction in void ratio and 47 times increase in transmitted amplitude,
398 while the looser specimen, LS1-2C28, experience 0.45 reduction in void ratio and 73 times
399 increase in transmitted amplitude.

400 Based on the slope of normalized amplitude graph, a transitional point is defined as the intersection
401 of two straight tangential lines passing through the initial and final part of the curve (Figure 8).
402 This transitional point decreases with void ratio as the yield stress, and occurs at normal stresses
403 close to mechanical yield stress. In this study, this transitional stress is interpreted as seismic yield
404 stress.

405
 406 Figure 8- Variation of normalized transmitted amplitude with normal stress for specimens with
 407 different initial void ratios, and the clarification on how to determine the seismic yield stress
 408

409 3-2 Effect of particle size

410 In this section, three compression tests on uniform specimens composed of sand No I, II and III
 411 are considered in which all three specimens were approximately prepared with the same initial
 412 void ratio of 0.48. Two compression/unloading cycles as described in table 2 were applied on these
 413 three specimens. These tests were performed to provide data on effect of particle size and inter-
 414 particle contact area on yield stress and ultrasonic measurements.

415 Void ratio changes for three uniformly graded specimens having initial void ratio of 0.48 and mean
 416 particle size of 0.35, 0.20 and 0.10 mm under one dimensional compression are presented in Figure
 417 9(a). Although all three samples were prepared in the same initial void ratio and subjected to
 418 similar loading path with the same loading rate, different mechanical behavior was observed for
 419 three specimens. As presented in Figure 9(a), the tested specimens experienced a decrease in their
 420 void ratio as a result of normal stress increase. However, the rate of change in void ratio were

421 different and the specimens composed of small particles experienced lower changes of void ratio
422 during compression. At 48 MPa normal stress, sand No. I, II and III experience 0.30, 0.27 and 0.25
423 reduction in void ratio respectively. This has the effect of shifting the compression curve to the
424 right which results in an increase in the yield stress. The yield stress for specimen composed of
425 sand No. I, II and III are 17, 19.5 and 21 MPa, respectively.

426 Ultrasonic measurements were conducted during the first and second compression/unloading
427 cycles, and similar to the compression curves, measured values of maximum transmitted amplitude
428 along different loading and unloading paths are shown in Figure 9(b). As the values of void ratio
429 are close for all specimen, the average particle coordination number for different specimens is
430 equal according to equation 1. However, specific surface area is inversely proportional to particle
431 radius and is more for smaller particles [74,75]. Increase in specific surface area leads to more
432 contact area for smaller particles in which more area is provided for ultrasonic waves to travel
433 through the soil particles.

434 The values of maximum transmitted amplitude are higher for specimens with smaller particles and
435 they increase nonlinearly during the compression. Maximum transmitted amplitude shows an
436 irreversible behavior similar to void ratio variations and the values did not reduce to their initial
437 values obtained in the first loading path.

439
 440 Figure 9- Impact of particle size on: a) void ratio and the values of yield stress, b) absolute
 441 values of transmitted amplitude, c) wave velocity, d) dominant frequency during compression
 442 and unloading cycles.

443 Changes in compressional wave velocity are presented in Figure 9 (c). In normal stresses below
 444 10 MPa, wave velocity is almost equal for three different specimens in agreement with [49,50].
 445 However, at higher normal stresses compressional wave velocity is slightly more for specimen
 446 with larger particles due to dependency of wave velocity on void ratio. Void ratio at 28 MPa normal
 447 stress is 0.25, 0.28 and 0.31 for sand No I, II and III respectively. This small difference in void
 448 ratio results in higher wave velocity values for sand No. I. In the unloading path, wave velocity
 449 experienced a light upward shift compare to the loading path and decreases nonlinearly.
 450 In this series of tests, dominant frequency for each specimen follows an increasing trend with a
 451 limiting maximum value with normal stress similar to tests DS1-2C28 and LS1-2C28. Figure 9(d)

452 shows the measured values of dominant frequency for tests DS1-2C28, DS2-2C28 and DS3-2C28.

453 This Figure indicates that in addition to void ratio and transmitted amplitude, dominant frequency

454 is a function of particle size and increases with decreasing particle size.

455 Figure 10 shows the evolution of normalized transmitted amplitude with normal stress for

456 specimens with different particle sizes. Mechanical behavior and compressibility of granular soils

457 is dependent on particle size and the compressibility increases with particles diameter. Variation

458 of normalize transmitted amplitude is higher for specimen DS1-2C28, showing that the amount of

459 increase in inter-particle contact area increases as the particles diameter increases. This would lower

460 the seismic yield stress for specimen with larger particles which is in agreement with observed

461 mechanical behavior and compressibility of soil specimens.

462 A comparison between yield stress and seismic yield stress for 6 specimens at two different initial

463 void ratios with different particles is provided in Figure 12. There is a good consistency between

464 obtained values for yield stress and seismic yield stress. This excellent repeatability provide

465 evidence that the impact of physical properties of soil assemblies like particle size and density are

466 detectable in variation of transmitted amplitude and is a suitable parameter to understand and

467 monitor the deformation of granular soil layers.

468

469 Figure 10- Variation of normalized transmitted amplitude with normal stress for specimens with
 470 different particle sizes and determination of seismic yield stress.

471

472 Figure 11. Comparison of yield stress and seismic yield stress for experiments conducted in this
 473 study with different initial void ratios and particle sizes.

474

475 **3-3 Effect of particle Crushing**

476 In addition to particle size and void ratio, the single particle tensile strength plays an important
477 role in compressional behavior and strength of granular materials. In soil assemblies, inter-
478 particle stresses that develop through force chains can lead to high local contact stress
479 concentrations and result in particle crushing even under low boundary stresses. In this section,
480 we aim at identifying the link between ultrasonic measurements and amount of grain crushing
481 under different levels of normal stresses.

482 Particle crushing is identified as one of the most critical mechanisms responsible for changes in
483 mechanical properties of a sand layer by changing grain size distribution [5,7]. In order to measure
484 evolution of particle crushing with boundary stresses, fifteen specimens were prepared from sand
485 No.I, II and III and at the initial void ratio of 0.48. Then, the specimens were loaded for one cycle
486 of loading-unloading up to 10, 20, 30 40, and 48 MPa normal stresses.

487 Sieve analysis was conducted for specimens after the loading and unloading cycle and amount of
488 crushed particles were determined based on the percentage of particles passing through sieve No.
489 60, 80, 100 and 200. Obtained soil distribution curves for sand No. I and No. II are presented in
490 Figure 12. In addition to sieve analysis, Figure 13 shows the SEM images taken from soil No. I
491 subjected to a compression cycle with maximum normal stress of 48 MPa. Comparing Figure 4(a)
492 and 13 (a) provide evidence that the number of fine particles and the original particles shape has
493 changed significantly with normal stress. Figure 13 illustrates how several soil particles suffered
494 from crushing, while some particles were remained intact even under 48 MPa normal stress.

495 Amount of crushed particles increases with increasing the applied normal stress on the specimen
496 and more specifically the D10 decreases considerably compared to D50 or D60. Table 4 and
497 Figure 14 present the progression in the amount of crushed particles corresponding to each normal
498 stress.

499

500

501

Figure 12- Particle soil distribution curve for sand No. I and No. II subjected to different amount of normal stress

502

503

504

505

Figure 13- SEM images with a)50, b)200 times magnification for sand No. I subjected to one cycle of compression with 48 MPa normal stress.

506

Table 4- Evolution in amount of crushed particles with normal stress for different particle sizes

Normal stress (MPa)	Sand No. I	Sand No. II	Sand No. III
0	19.3	16.9	2.1
20	27	25.6	4.9

30	34.2	30.5	6.6
40	39.7	34.9	8.9
48	43	37.4	11.2

507

508 Crushing of granular materials is experimentally known to be dependent on particle mineralogy,
 509 particle size and coordination number. In these experiments, changes in amount of particle
 510 crushing is just due to particle size as all specimens were prepared with quartz sand at the same
 511 initial void ratio. The amount of crushed particles is higher for larger particle and increases with
 512 normal stress, while the rate of increase is not constant and more particles experience crushing
 513 for normal stresses lower than 20 MPa, as shown in Figure 14.

514

515 Figure 14- The amount of crushed particles corresponding to each level of normal
 516 stress for sand No. I, No. II and No. III

517 Ultrasonic measurements were carried out during compression of granular soil layer. Measured
 518 values of dominant frequency during compression of granular layer are presented for three types
 519 of particles in Figure 15. As discussed in previous section, dominant frequency values increase
 520 with the normal stress and the values are higher for smaller particles. Figure 15 shows the
 521 normalized values of dominant frequency with respect to their initial values. Variation of

522 normalized dominant frequency shows an opposite trend with the absolute values and changes in
523 normalized values are higher for larger particles.

524

525

526 Figure 15- Impact of particle size on variation of a) dominant frequency, b) normalized dominant
527 frequency during compression.

528

529 According to Displacement Discontinuity Theory, fractures and voids in rock materials behave
530 like a filter tending to transmit low frequency contents of the wave [40,76]. In rock fractures, with
531 increasing compression the transmitted wave grows and the frequencies at which the wave travels
532 change with the stiffness of the rock fracture [77-79].

533 Similar variations were observed in soil materials, and ultrasonic waves can transmit better with
534 higher frequency contents in dense granular soil packing with lower inter-particle pore volume.

535 In specimens prepared with sand No. III, pore volumes between the soil particle are smaller
536 compare to specimens prepared with sand No. I, as the diameter of particles is smaller.

537 Compressional waves pass with a higher frequency contents through specimen composed of sand
538 with smaller particles. However, the rate of changes in dominant frequency values follows an

539 opposite trend and is not equal for all specimens (Figure 15b). Normalized dominant frequency

540 is related to the changes in volume and distribution of inter-particle pores in a soil assembly, and
541 during compression of granular materials, particle crushing is the main mechanism responsible
542 for changes in volume of inter-particle pores.

543 In soil assemblies especially with uniform particle gradation, three factors are important for
544 particle survival: particle size, coordination number, and distribution of particle sizes. Smaller
545 particles are experimentally known to be stronger under impact and compression stresses [8,80].

546 Thus, the amount of crushed particles is higher for larger particles. On the other hand, particle

547 crushing is more for soil assemblies with uniform particle size gradation. This observation is due

548 to the high stress concentrations on particle surface in a uniform soil packing. This stress

549 concentration can cause particle crushing even at low level of confining stresses and as a results

550 percentage of fine particles increases in the soil assembly. Produced fine particles can move into

551 the gaps between the particles and fill the voids and govern a denser soil structure. This

552 densification would help ultrasonic waves to travel with higher frequency content and also

553 distribute the external stresses better on the particles surface. The stress redistribution leads to

554 lower contact stresses on the surface of single particle and make the soil particle invulnerable to

555 higher normal stresses. Evolution in particle crushing versus normalized dominant frequency is

556 plotted in Figure 16. The trend for three sand types is almost linear with evolution in normal

557 stress. The slope for each line is dependent on the particle size and increases with particle size.

558 Mechanical behavior of granular materials including weak or high strength particles was observed

559 to follow a similar trend [7]; however, the level of stresses varies with different materials

560 depending on the mineralogy of particle. Therefore, the observed linear relationship can be

561 successfully implemented to evaluate particle crushing for variety of particles with various

562 mineralogy and sizes in geotechnical systems or fault gouges.

563

564 Figure 16- Linear relationship between the amount of crushed particles and normalized
 565 dominant frequency for three soils with different particle sizes

566

567 **Conclusion:**

568 We developed a one dimensional compression setup equipped with ultrasonic transducers to
 569 continuously monitor a granular soil layer during compression and investigate the correlation
 570 between mechanisms occurring during compression of granular soils with ultrasonic wave
 571 characterizations. Compressional wave properties including amplitude, velocity and dominant
 572 frequency were analyzed through recorded waveforms with a high resolution data acquisition
 573 system. Measured properties of ultrasonic waves specially wave velocity are consistent with
 574 previous studies, and new and novel observations of variations in amplitude and frequency of
 575 waves were made in granular materials. We observed that transmitted amplitude depends on the
 576 true contact area between the particles and increases with normal stress and decreasing particle
 577 size. Changes in transmitted amplitude are related to mechanisms controlling the granular soil
 578 structure and force chain arrangements, including particle slippage, deformation and crushing. A

579 new seismic yield stress term corresponding to transitional stress in the slope of normalized
580 transmitted amplitude is introduced. The seismic yield stress was found to occur at normal stresses
581 close to yield stress and could be a suitable parameter to estimate general behavior of granular
582 soil layers. The behavior of granular materials is also a function of particle size and particle
583 crushing. In this study, a relationship was found between particle size and subsequently the
584 volume of inter-particle pore size with dominant frequency. It was observed that compressional
585 waves travel with higher frequency contents through specimens composed of smaller particles.
586 However, changes in dominant frequency is more for larger particles and a linear correlation was
587 observed between normalized dominant frequency variation and amount of crushed particles as a
588 result of increase in normal stress. These results can be extended to other type of granular
589 materials to monitor and estimate the mechanical behavior of granular soils in geotechnical
590 structures or gouge materials.

591

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